

SOME THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract. The article emphasizes the role of entrepreneurial entities in developing the national economy, the economic role of the state in forming a market economy, and how this guarantees the success of economic reforms. The article theoretically examines various views and definitions of entrepreneurship as a category, its essence, the income received by entrepreneurs and their participation in implementing state socio-economic programs, and the fact that entrepreneurial abilities differ and develop differently among individuals.

Keywords: entrepreneurial activity, category of owners, national model, economic category, income, economic independence, economic responsibility, risk, entrepreneurial ability, free competition.

Achieving sustainable, crisis-free, and effective development of our national economy under market economy conditions largely depends on utilizing the potential and opportunities of existing material and labor resources in our country's regions and increasing their activity.

The economic reforms being implemented in our republic are characterized by the creation of organizational, legal, and economic conditions necessary for the development of entrepreneurship. The development of business entities based on market requirements is certainly a new way for us to develop the national economy, and business enterprises should conduct their activities taking into account the demands of the consumer market.

A market economy is an economy in which the markets for goods and

services, money and capital, securities, and labor are interconnected; the path to such an economy is not uniform. Uzbekistan has created its own national model of transition to a market economy, in the implementation of which the following important features can be distinguished:

- social orientation towards achieving the end result that ensures an increase in people's well-being;

- solving the problem of economic stabilization with minimal social costs and ensuring employment of the able-bodied population by accelerating macroeconomic growth;

- ensuring and strengthening the necessary conditions for the functioning of the market mechanism, where the activities of economic entities are determined based on the criterion of maximum efficiency, under the influence of the law of value, supply and demand;

- Gradual abandonment of direct state management of production, granting freedoms to producers themselves based on economic expediency, the specifics of activity types, the necessary volume and variety of manufactured products, and the scale of production and economic ties;

- Ensuring the country's economic independence in selecting priority areas for investment and innovation policy and attracting foreign capital. Structural restructuring of the economy, providing for the fullest use of the advantages of the international division of labor;

- It consists of pursuing a strong social policy aimed primarily at targeted protection of the low-income segment of the population at all stages of market economy formation.

The main goal of national economic policy is the gradual creation of the foundations of a developed and socially oriented market economy. At the same time, its driving force and the feasibility of its long-term plans lie in the category of property owners. The formation of a genuine class of property owners in our

republic is a guarantee of the irreversibility of the reform process. It is the economic force that creates the conditions for establishing a market economy and drives changes towards a market economy.

The formation of a developed market economy does not mean the state's abandonment of economic regulation. On the contrary, the state's role in guiding economic and social processes strengthens, and its methods and instruments for influencing the economy are refined. From this perspective, state regulation of the market economy is an essential condition for economic development and stability. State regulation of the market economy is the key to successful economic reforms and a guarantee of the well-being of the people and society.

Certainly, the state's influence on the economy is primarily exercised through its impact on business entities. Business and entrepreneurship represent economic management and relationships between economic entities in a specific field. Business and entrepreneurship are activities aimed at achieving certain economic benefits or generating income by independently risking personal property based on one's own responsibilities. Business and entrepreneurship possess two distinct characteristics. On one hand, there is the characteristic of economic interest, and on the other hand, the characteristic of risk-taking, which falls upon the entrepreneur.

Entrepreneurship is not only a category of market economy; it is a historical economic category. People's entrepreneurial activities have been carried out in all socio-economic conditions. In a market economy, people's entrepreneurial activities begin to be implemented on a wide scale. The main reason for this is the formation of middle-class property owners and the foundation of economic relations on free competition. It should be noted that there is virtually no single generalized view among economists regarding the scientific and theoretical disclosure of the essence of the "entrepreneurship" category. The main reason for this, in our opinion, is expressed through the historical development of entrepreneurial activities in various forms of ownership, its economic and social

aspects, and the study of society from a class perspective.

The English economist A. Smith, in assessing entrepreneurial activity based on the conditions of capitalist production, came to the following conclusion. Paying special attention to the "invisible hand" and freedom of competition in a market economy, he showed that in market conditions, each of its objects acts independently, but in pursuing their economic interests through the "invisible hand," they often serve the interests of society more than they consciously strive for.

Entrepreneurship is an economic category, where an entrepreneur is a participant in the economic process of society, seeking new technologies and ways to satisfy societal needs in order to obtain profit. The entrepreneurial abilities of individuals are manifested in their capacity to make decisions necessary for the planned and rational use of production resources involved in the manufacturing process, to actively participate in innovation processes, and to achieve designated goals through risk-taking in existing entrepreneurial activities. Can everyone's activities be evaluated from an entrepreneurial perspective? Certainly not. For instance, the mere production of goods necessary for society does not represent entrepreneurship. This is simply a standard production process. Entrepreneurial activity is defined as the organization of production where the main goal is to obtain a certain level of income. To achieve this, the manufacturing entrepreneur must ensure the sale of their products through economic relations with consumers.

Therefore, an entrepreneur's economic activity related to production can be considered entrepreneurial activity only when the goal of producing a certain product and delivering it to consumers is to generate a certain level of income. Is entrepreneurial activity always characterized by receiving a certain income? Of course not. Sometimes, entrepreneurs increase production costs by purchasing new production technologies using the income they receive. However, these production costs will ensure the growth of the entrepreneur's income in the future.

Entrepreneurial activity can be considered as such only if it ensures that all participants involved in production and service provision receive a certain income.

Entrepreneurship can be carried out by individuals, sole proprietors, groups, collectives, and organizations. Entrepreneurial activity can be implemented not only at the enterprise level but also at the state level. The state, as a rule, can participate in entrepreneurship by investing a certain amount, providing production technologies, or allocating production space. In a market economy, private entrepreneurship can also be involved in implementing state socio-economic programs.

An entrepreneur must constantly be proactive and strive for innovation. Only by seeking innovations, organizing production according to the demands of the times, and striving to produce products that meet world standards can one achieve a steady income. In other words, an entrepreneur should aim to:

- organize the production of goods based on new technologies, taking into account the market's law of supply and demand;
- attract consumers by continuously improving the quality of manufactured products;
- engage the savings of the inactive population and foreign currency in entrepreneurial activities;
- conduct economic analysis of information on market economy development and fully utilize it;
- attract cost-effective labor and raw materials to production by improving production technologies in line with modern requirements.

Entrepreneurial activity is fundamentally based on economic independence and economic responsibility. An entrepreneur primarily relies on their personal abilities, knowledge, and resources. Regardless of how substantial the support for entrepreneurship may be from the state or other entities, it cannot be the decisive factor in terms of the entrepreneur's independence and responsibility. Since

entrepreneurship is an activity characteristic of market relations, it is threatened by risks associated with market uncertainty, probability, and the variability of various conditions. Importantly, the risks associated with these uncertainties are borne by the entrepreneur.

Entrepreneurial ability or the aspiration for entrepreneurship exists in every person to some degree. It should be noted that entrepreneurship occupies a very important place in our national mentality and values. In particular, the famous words of Amir Timur, the great conqueror, expressing that one courageous and enterprising person is superior to tens of thousands of indifferent and incompetent people, also reflect this sentiment.

At the same time, due to the fact that entrepreneurial activities develop differently in various individuals, and many factors influence the manifestation of this ability, the number of people with real entrepreneurial abilities and opportunities is not unlimited.

Low production efficiency, economic difficulties, and the unskilled use of market mechanism levers are directly linked to the insufficient utilization of the human entrepreneurial factor.

As a result of the widespread development of entrepreneurial activity, it becomes possible to satisfy the population's demand for consumer goods and the production sector's need for raw materials and means of production at affordable prices. Business and entrepreneurship are of great importance not only for individuals but also for society and the state. They contribute to solving socio-economic problems facing the state that need to be addressed. The great economist Adam Smith, defining entrepreneurial activity, stated that an entrepreneur's income is the payment received for implementing business ideas based on risk-taking. Max Weber, a prominent scholar in management systems, considered entrepreneurship to be the most important and effective activity in the economy, while Joseph Schumpeter defined entrepreneurship as the main factor in economic development.

The English economist John Maynard Keynes emphasized that entrepreneurship is a new form of economic management. It embodies caution, foresight, calculation, striving for good, independence, entrepreneurship, leaving wealth to heirs, and frugality.

Everyone can participate in entrepreneurial activity, but it should be noted that only people who have developed entrepreneurial qualities to a certain extent can engage in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs are constantly searching and carrying out their activities under constant economic risk.

The improvement of entrepreneurial activities based on market demands and free competition can solve the economic problems facing the republic at the level of domestic and foreign market requirements.

The development and enhancement of entrepreneurial activities is the main pressing issue of our time. It cannot be said that the organizational, legal, and economic conditions necessary for entrepreneurial activity fully meet the requirements of the republic's industrial sectors. The development of entrepreneurial activity in a liberalized market economy is linked to the improvement of the financial, credit, and tax systems. In a market economy, the development of entrepreneurial activity, as the main factor, ensures the elimination and prevention of economic crises.

The primary task of entrepreneurship is to create new supply markets through the production of new in-demand products. Considering the consumption patterns of new consumers in the market, the development of entrepreneurial activities has two main directions: firstly, to ensure the growth of their economic activities by developing new production processes and manufacturing innovative products that meet market demands; and secondly, to open and develop new consumer markets.

In conclusion, entrepreneurship is the main factor of production, representing not only the ability to work but also the scientific potential and experience embodied in an individual, as expressed through their effective organizational,

managerial, and economic activities in the production process.

The effectiveness of entrepreneurship is the result of cooperative labor, its growth being reflected in the level of utilization of equipment and production technologies, the increase in labor productivity, the efficient use of working hours, and the improvement of labor quality.

List of references:

1. Rashidov R. Systemic Characteristics of Entrepreneurial Economic Activity. Business-Expert Journal, Issue 11, 2022.
2. Smith A. An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations. Moscow, 1962.
3. Schumpeter J. Theory of Economic Development: A Study of Entrepreneurial Profit, Capital, Credit, Interest, and the Business Cycle. Moscow: Progress, 1982.
4. Gofurov U.V. Improving the Economic Mechanisms of State Regulation of Small Business. Tashkent, 2017.